

**AHMED YASSAVI IS A GREAT REPRESENTATIVE
OF SUFISM LITERATURE**

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Abstract. Yassavi, Khwaja Ahmed Yassavi (Sayram city near Yassi, about the second half of the 11th century - 1166) is one of the famous representatives of Sufism, a great poet of the Turkic peoples. His father, Sheikh Ibrahim, was one of the most influential people of the Javonmard sect. Yassavi wrote in the Chigatoi language.

Key words: literature, religion, language, creativity, science

Soon after Yassavi's birth, his mother, Musa Sheikh's daughter Aisha Khatun, died. He was separated from his father at the age of 7. His sister Gavhar Shahnoz is busy with his elementary education. After moving to Yassi with his sister, Yassavi meets and learns from his teacher, Grandpa Arslan ("At the age of seven, I looked for Grandpa Arslan..."). Yassavi Yassida perfectly mastered the secrets of inner science. At that time, scholars from different parts of Turkestan gathered in Bukhara, which was one of the centers of knowledge in Movorunnahr. Yassavi also goes to Bukhara under the instructions of Grandfather Arslan. He met Sheikh Yusuf Hamadani, the leading scientist and Sufi of the time, and became a murid of him. In Bukhara, he studied Persian as well as Arabic. They get acquainted with mystical literature created in Persian. He communicates and consults with Khwaja Abdukholiq Gijduvani, Abdullah Barqi, Khwaja Hasan Andoqi, and is among the murids of Yusuf Hamadani.

About Alisher Navoi Yassavi, he says, "His authority is high and famous, his merits are outstanding and infamous. He is an excellent disciple and companion, and he is extremely humble under the will and sincerity of the king." This idea refers to the time when Yassavi returned to Yassi and became famous as a murshid who founded a new sect. Yassavi also used poetry in order to attract more Turkic peoples to Islam and deeply instill the ideas of Sufism into the hearts of the masses. Abdurauf Fitrat said that Yasavi's "path in literature is the dark path of our simple folk poets... His wisdom is equal in weight, rhyme, and style to poems called folk literature." He wrote a work that will be a warning not only to the Turkish people, but also to the whole world.

In Yassavi's view, wisdom is "ilmi laduni", i.e. the knowledge of the unseen, and it also has the meaning of discovering divine secrets. Yassavi himself did not create any book under the name "Devoni Hikmat". This rare work was ordered by his murid and followers. But this does not give grounds for the claim that the complex of wisdom has nothing to do with Yassavi. Commenting on Sufi Olloyar Yassavi, he also said: Shariat was ul oftobe, Qalibdur us ul erdin kitabe.

In "Devoni Hikmat" the concepts of divine love and infatuation, the bliss of enlightenment and enlightenment, and the transition from death to life are illuminated in extremely sincere and touching tones. Not all poems in "Devoni Hikmat" belong to Yassavi. It also includes examples of the works of Yassavi's followers. This, of course, caused certain changes in the language and style of proverbs. But none of Yassavi's dozens of followers changed the ideological, moral, spiritual, and ideological direction started by their teachers. This is fully confirmed by dozens of ancient sources discussing Yassavi's life, sect and art, especially Sultan Ahmad Hazini's work "Jawahir ul-Abror min Amwajil Bihar".

Not only Yassavi's art, but also how long he lived and when he died are controversial. In one of his wisdoms, he says, "I entered one hundred and twenty-five, but I couldn't tell." These words have a metaphorical meaning rather than a historical truth. Moreover, spending more than half of a long life of 125 years "underground" ("I went underground at sixty-three," says Yassavi) is an incredible phenomenon. However, most researchers recorded the date of his death as 1166-67.

For a long time, it was not possible to scientifically research Yasavi's life and work. His works were not allowed to be published. In the 70s of the last century, attempts to properly assess Yasavi's services in the history of national culture, language and literature were condemned. On the eve of independence, in particular, after the independence of Uzbekistan, a new era began in legal studies. Initially, copies of "Devoni Hikmat" were published in various newspapers and magazines, and in 1990-92, 2 independent editions of it were delivered to readers. These publications not only in Uzbekistan, but also in other Turkic countries increased interest in the life, literary and educational activities of this great mystic, and the service of his followers. In 1993, scientific conferences dedicated to Yassavi were held in Uzbekistan, and the text of the lectures was published in a separate collection. The press published articles discussing Yassavi's personality, sect, and poetry. Several streets and neighborhoods in Uzbekistan are called Yassavi. The foundations of the Yassawi sect are reflected in sources and treatises such as "Faqrnama" (some attribute it

to Yassawi), "Maslakul-arifin", "Lama'ot", "Samaratul-mashoyikh", "Javahir ul-Abror". The book "Divoni Hikmat" was organized by the students of the book. It is led by the idea of divine love and educational content. The proverbs are deeply connected to the Holy Qur'an and the hadiths of Muhammad, peace be upon him, with an emphasis on meaning and essence. More than 20 copies of "Divoni Hikmat" are stored in the OR FA SHI fund. The oldest of the manuscripts of the work belongs to the 17th century.

Yassavi Heritage and Sect Abroad L. Massignon, A. Arberry, M. Smitt, H. Kiesling, F. Mayer, A. Schimmel, R. Hartman, F. Koprulu, J. Trimingham, K. Eraslon, Idris Shokh, Devin Dee Wis; In Russia, A. Krinsky, I. Petrushevsky, E. Bertels; It was studied in Uzbekistan by Fitrat, A. Sa'diy, E. Rustamov, B. Kasimov, I. Hakkulov, N. Hasanov.

His tomb was repaired by Amir Temur in Turkistan, Kazakhstan, in the 14th century. There is a Turkish-Kazakh university named after Ahmed Yassavi in Turkestan.

Research is being conducted to create the image of Yassavi in artistic creation. The writer Sadulla Siyoyev published the 1st book (1994) of the novel "The Last Journey of Yassavi".

References:

1. Phytrate. Ahmad Yasawi. "Selected Works" (prepared for publication by H. Boltaboev). Volume 2. — T.: Spirituality, 2000;
2. A. Sa'di. Who was Yasavi? (prepared for publication. B. Dostkaraev) - T.: 1994.
3. E. Rustamov. The sound of history and life in the wisdom of Ahmad Yasavi. Journal "Uzbek language and literature". 1972, No. 4-5;
4. I. Haqqul. Ahmad Yasawi. His life and creative path. — T.: 2001.
5. N. Hasanov. Law studies in Turkey. - T.: 1999

